

FAMILY AND VALUE

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Annotation

In the article, the author showed that the main content and purpose of family life is to raise children, to be able to set an example of kindness in the formation of a perfect and creative personality. The personal example of parents, first of all, the spiritual and moral qualities of their pupils is the main principle of education, and in this the child learns the rules of the worldview, positive attitude to work, respect for family members and others, understanding of national values from the family.

Key words: family, atmosphere, lesson, virtue, education and upbringing, value, motherland, love, consequence.

Family has always occupied one of the most important places among the values of human life. Because all people at different stages of life are directly related to family, it is a natural part of life. Family is one of the most important values in life, and as the importance of family in human life, it is assigned a place among other important things such as work, friends, leisure, politics and religion.

Family and school (in the broadest sense) are social institutions, the first place where knowledge, good profession, communication skills, independence, sense of responsibility for oneself, loved ones and ultimately for the fate of the country where one is located are brought up. Kindness, patriotism, citizenship, work and creativity, literature and art, science and other values, which are included

in the list of basic national values in the family, form a set of general concepts that are passed from generation to generation in the form of examples.

The concept of "family" is a set of close relatives, parents with children living together and other close relatives; The circle of persons related to property is a small group based on the rights and obligations of marriage or blood relations arising through adoption or other forms. A family is a group of relatives who have the appropriate rights and obligations and who spread out from a common house and support each other.

From a legal point of view, the provisions on the family are mentioned in these several articles of the Constitution of Uzbekistan. In Article 73 of the Constitution of Uzbekistan, the rights and obligations of parents regarding the education and upbringing of children are written as follows:

Parents have the right and obligation to educate their children. Parents are responsible for the upbringing and development of their children. They must take care of their children's health, physical, mental, spiritual and moral development. In Article 8, about the application of local customs and traditions in family relations, "In the absence of relevant norms for the regulation of family relations in the legislation, local customs and traditions that do not contradict the principles of the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan shall be used." it is indicated that. [1]

In the process of education at school, the process of education is carried out in cooperation with parents and teachers. In nine or eleven years of study, children, adults, parents, as a team, move with stability and certain spatial-temporal boundaries, carrying out various activities in the implementation of common goals and tasks. In this, we must not forget the cooperation between primary family and school.

As V.A. Sukhomlinsky said: "The main meaning and purpose of family life is raising children. The main school of raising children is the formation of a perfect and creative person by the mutual understanding of husband and wife, father and mother. The family is the main environment in which love is taught. The personal example of parents primarily contributes to the spiritual and moral qualities of their students and their activeness, and teaches them to have a life position, worldview

rules, a positive attitude to work, to treat family members and others with respect, and to understand national values.

In the encyclopedic dictionary of philosophy, the concept of value is given the following definition. Value is a philosophical-sociological and axiological concept used to show the universal, social-ethical, cultural-spiritual significance of certain events in reality. All things, events and events that are important for society, man and humanity: freedom, goodness, equality, peace, truth, enlightenment, culture, material and spiritual wealth, monuments, beauty, moral character and virtues, traditions, customs, udum and others were considered[2] Values can be universal, universal, national, regional personal. Values are a concept that has its own historical roots, development, inheritance as a product of socio-historical development, first of all, production, labor activities are created as a set of things, events, behaviors that benefit relations between people, and the activities of certain people, social groups. it is becoming a spiritual phenomenon that directs the behavior in a certain direction and sets the appropriate norm.

In the family, a national personality based on national values, a patriot of his homeland should be brought up. With the help of national values, education will educate the young generation in the spirit of respect for national traditions and customs, character, and the formation of relations with the environment.

It is very important for the young generation of an independent country to understand the importance and greatness of national values. Independent Uzbekistan always needs citizens who have grown up through national values, patriots of the country, and those who know the role of national pedagogy and universal values. It is necessary to educate a person who respects culture, traditions, religion, history, language, people, motherland, state, who is ready to sacrifice his knowledge and abilities for his homeland. The educational traditions of the Uzbek people are not inferior to the traditions of other nations, and there are many aspects that can serve as an example. Thus, while educating the young generation in the spirit of priceless folk traditions and customs, we must inculcate in them the most important foundations for becoming individuals, patriots, and citizens.

Dignity includes respect for a person and recognition of his rights. Dignity arises as an important aspect of social and moral freedom of a person. Values have a social nature and appear and develop in the course of people's practical activities.

Values are the incomparable wealth of our people. It is our sacred duty to carefully create, develop and enrich it. That's why today our free and free nation boldly strives for new and advanced aspects in science and technology, culture and art in the enlightenment created by all nations and states. In the land of Uzbek, which happens many times in history, a unique and progressive, talented, and most importantly necessary value system is being established.

In everyday communication, many people are used to using the expression of value to refer to something, event, event, feature, etc., which has value. But it is sad that its meaning in everyday life is transferred to scientific literature. Scientific debates and philosophical discussions about values will always continue. Because the spiritual-intellectual development of society, the needs of humanity are in constant motion.

Literature:

1. Articles 73-8 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan.
2. Philosophy. Encyclopedic dictionary. 2004.
3. Wikipedia. Information from the National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan (2000-2005) was used.